

A CRITICAL EXAMINATION OF THE HISTORICAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CLASSICAL ISLAMIC LAW AND ENGLISH COMMON LAW

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ABSTRACT

A significant turning point in the development of the English legal system occurred in the 12th century with the foundation of common law under King Henry II of England. Although the origins of this legal system are typically found in Roman and Canon law traditions, historians continue to disagree over whether Islamic legal institutions had any direct influence. Sicily's identity was greatly shaped by Arab civilisation, which ruled the island for over 200 years until the Norman Knights conquered it in 1061. This research aims to investigate the historical relationships between the common law of England and certain legal doctrines found in classical Islamic law as it was applied in Arab Sicily. This study explores the historical roots of this legal concept. It compares and contrasts the two legal systems, emphasising features like trust (*waqf*), the supremacy of law over the State, individual liberties, contract freedom, judicial impartiality, and the *res judicata* doctrine. This investigation reveals how the interplay between common law and Islamic legal traditions has shaped legal systems all over the world, highlighting the value of cross-cultural dialogue and respect for one another in the development of legal frameworks. This analysis highlights the dynamic character of legal growth through cross-cultural impacts and improves our understanding of legal history.

Keywords: Common Law; Islamic Law; Arab Sicily; Legal System; Islamic Jurisprudence.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of legal systems is a complex process that is influenced by various factors, such as culture, geography, and history.^[1] Many scholars have been exploring whether fundamental principles of classical Islamic law were borrowed into the common law of England. These principles include trust (*waqf*), the importance of law over the State, individualism, freedom of contract, impartial judicial oversight, and the doctrine of *res judicata*. This study aims to critically examine the historical connections between classical Islamic law, as applied in Arab Sicily, and certain legal principles found in the common law of England.

Sicily is a crucial island controlling trade routes across the Mediterranean Sea.^[2] It has been a melting pot of different civilisations throughout history,^[3] witnessing a complex series of conquests by the Greeks, Phoenicians, Romans, Byzantines, Arabs, Normans, and Spanish.^[4] These conquests have left an indelible mark on the island's language, culture, legal systems, agriculture, art, and architecture.^[5] The Arab civilisation played a significant role in shaping Sicily's identity, having ruled the island for over two centuries.^[6] Sicily was part of *Dar al-Islam*,^[7] (a country where the power lies with Muslims, where the rules of Islam are implemented and Islamic rituals are performed)^[8] until it was conquered by the Norman Knights led by Roger de Hauteville, or Roger I (r. 1071–1101), and his brother Robert de Guiscard (b. 1015-1085),^[9] in 1061 and finally concluded in 1091.^[10]

In the 12th century, Henry II, King of England (r. 1154–1189) established the common law, leading to revolutionary changes in the English legal system.^[11] Key developments included the introduction of the action of debt, the assize of novel disseisin, and the implementation of trial by jury. These institutions are believed to have been influenced by the civil law traditions of Roman and Canon law.^[12] However, some historians also suggest that these institutions may have direct origins in Islamic legal institutions.^[13] However, this is hotly debated.^[14]

The question at hand is how the common law of England drew inspiration from certain Islamic principles originating from Arab Sicily during that period. In this comprehensive examination, we will explore the available historical evidence,

legal texts, and scholarly perspectives to assess the potential influence of classical Islamic law on the common law of England.

The analysis of this article also delves into the origins of these legal concepts and conducts a comparative study to highlight similarities and differences between the two legal systems, focusing on aspects such as trust (*waqf*), the primacy of law over the State, individual rights, contractual freedom, judicial impartiality, and the doctrine of *res judicata*.

THE HISTORICAL CONTEXT: THE CONNECTION OF ARAB SICILY AND ENGLAND DURING THE 12TH CENTURY

The Norman rule in Sicily during the last period of the 11th and early 12th centuries was not a time of cultural eradication but rather a time of integration and acceptance.^[15] The Normans embraced the unique features of Islamic culture and allowed the Muslim community to continue practising their customs freely.^[16] Christians, including Roman Catholics and Greek Orthodox, and Jews were allowed to practise their faiths if they paid a special tax called *jizya*.^[17] Many Muslim observers who visited Sicily and encountered the Norman kingdom praised the Norman Kings for adopting several Muslim rules and customs.^[18] They went as far as to propagate this idea, highlighting that the inclusion of Islamic jurists in the Norman *Curia Regis* (King's Court) was not a sign of submission but rather an acknowledgement of the social and cultural significance of the Muslim community.^[19]

Under Roger I, the Muslim soldiers remained loyal, facing penalties if they abandoned their religion.^[20] When Roger I passed away, his son, Roger II (r. 1130–1154), succeeded him and became the king of Sicily, Apulia, Calabria, and Capua, and he continued to consolidate numerous Norman territories under his rule in Southern Italy and Northern Africa.^[21] The success of Roger II's military campaigns reintroduced Sicily's predominantly Islamic culture into the mainstream of European politics.^[22]

During the same period, the legal system in Sicily was organised based on Islamic principles. The judges were aided by a group of respected individuals, known as

boni homines (trusted people), typically Muslims from the local area.^[23] These judges were responsible for resolving property disputes, overseeing transactions, and handling minor civil cases involving Christians, much like the Muslim judges (*qadi*) who had been doing the same for the Muslim community in Sicily.^[24]

During this period, the Sicilian legal code was also enacted.^[25] There was a legal exchange between Muslims and Westerners over the Assizes (Constitution) of King Roger.^[26] The Assizes comprehensively regulated various aspects of life and drew influence not only from Norman-French law but also from Muslim and Byzantine legal traditions.^[27] It was notably progressive for its time.^[28] The preamble of Roger II's code acknowledged the diverse population under his rule. It stated that existing usages, customs, and laws would only be set aside if they contradicted his edicts.^[29]

Henry II became the King of England in 1154, the same year Roger II of Sicily passed away.^[30] As Henry II succeeded Roger II, he had the opportunity to learn from the latter's accomplishments.^[31] Henry II was a powerful and ambitious mediaeval monarch deeply interested in the law and eager to acquire power and wealth. He was impressed by the prosperity of Palermo, the capital of Sicily, which alone generated more income than the entire kingdom of England.^[32]

The question of how England established relations with Norman Sicily to the extent that Henry II was interested in studying and adopting the administrative system that contributed to Roger II's achievements has been addressed by Professor Charles Homer Haskins' study. Although limited, his findings can assist in this analysis. According to Professor Haskins, the main factors that answer the question of how England formed relations with Arab Sicily at that time are as follows:

- (1) The forms of government and courts in Northern and Southern Normandy exhibited potential mutual influence.^[33] Relationships arose due to trade and culture factors, allowing each party to benefit from each other's experiences in dealing with similar issues.^[34]

- (2) King Henry II tended to study administrative models from other countries and apply them in his own country, regardless of the model's origin. Conversely, King Roger II specifically investigated the practices of kings from other countries to implement them if deemed important.^[35]
- (3) The relationship between King Henry II and King Roger II became closer when the son of King Roger II, King William I, and the daughter of King Henry II, Princess Joan,^[36] married on 13 February 1177.^[37] This royal marriage opened opportunities for both of them to continue monitoring conditions and drawing inspiration from each other's administrative systems.^[38] For instance, Thomas Brown, a Sicilian official who was sent to the Court of Henry II, demonstrated his ability as a valuable source of information on the administrative and economic system in Sicily.^[39]

In summary, the close relationship between Arab Sicily and England in the 12th century was built through a blend of cultural, religious, military, economic, legal, and diplomatic factors. The Norman rulers of Sicily fostered religious tolerance and embraced Islamic culture, which led to a rich cultural exchange. Military successes under Roger II consolidated Norman territories while reintroducing Sicily's Islamic culture into European politics. Legal and administrative models in Sicily influenced by Islamic principles drew the interest of Henry II, contributing to cross-cultural legal exchange. Trade relations, economic interests, and the prosperity of Palermo were also key factors. Royal marriages and personal relationships facilitated direct communication and the exchange of information. Ultimately, this complex web of factors underscored the depth and significance of the historical connection between Arab Sicily and England during this period.

ISLAMIC LEGAL PRACTICE IN ARAB SICILY DURING THE NORMAN CONQUEST

Before the Norman conquest, Sicily, including Italy, Ifriqiya (now known as Tunisia), and North Africa^[40] was part of the Byzantine Empire in the 7th century.^[41] In the 8th century, Muslims gradually gained control of Taranto and Bari between 840 and 880, both of which had emirs. The Muslim population at that time was divided compared to the Christian population due to ethnic factions (Arabs, Berbers, Persians, Tartars, Negroes, etc) and sectarian factions (Sunni, Shia, and Ibadite) fighting among themselves throughout Islamic rule, leading to the decline of the Islamic kingdom in Sicily. This decline provided an opportunity for continued conquest.^[42]

For example, in the 10th and early 11th centuries, the Sunni Aghlabid dynasty, the original conquerors of Sicily, was overthrown by the Shia Fatimids from North Africa.^[43] This regime adhered to Ismaili Islamic jurisprudence.^[44] However, after the removal of the Fatimids in the mid-11th century, they returned to the allegiance of the Abbasid rule, and the Muslim population gradually adopted the Maliki Islamic jurisprudence, which was later fully implemented during Norman rule.^[45]

Two Maliki scholars serving as *lafif* (Islamic Jury) were appointed from Ifriqiya: Al-Lakhmi (d. 1085) from al-Qayrawan and residing in Sfax; and Al-Mazari (d. 1141) born in Mazara in Sicily and residing in al-Mahdiyya.^[46] Therefore, during Norman rule, it can be concluded that the Muslim population in Sicily practised Maliki Islamic jurisprudence.^[47]

It is noteworthy that famous Maliki jurists existed during the Fatimid and Kalbite rule, including Yahya ibn Umar (d. 903), Maymun ibn' Amr (d. 928), Dicana ibn Muhammad (d. 909), Abu Jafar Marwazi (sought his way to Sicily in 905), Luqman ibn Yusuf (d. 930), Abu Muhammad Hasan b Ali, Ibn Yunus (d. 1059), Abd al-Haqq ibn Muhammad Qurashi, Muhammad ibn 'Ali at-Tamimi (d. 1142), Ibn Makki, and Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Hasan ar-Rubai (d.1142). These scholars made Sicily a significant centre of intellectual activity and, through their travels, a major stream in Islamic scholarship.^[48]

ANALYSIS OF ISLAMIC PRINCIPLES ADOPTED BY ENGLISH COMMON LAW FROM ARAB SICILY

Professor John Makdisi concludes that in the 12th century, only England and Sicily had Norman kings who had a strong sense of nationality.^[49] This sense of nationality was reflected in their common institutions. The reigns of King Roger II in Sicily and King Henry II in England had many similar features, such as the treasuries that administered taxation and finance, the high courts that administered justice, and the chanceries that directed and coordinated the work of the other departments.^[50] Historians have often noted the resemblance between these two States.^[51] According to him, the royal English contract protected by the action of debt is identified with the Islamic *aqd*, the English assize of novel disseisin is identified with the Islamic *istihqaq* and the English jury is identified with the Islamic *lafif* in Maliki jurisprudence.^[52] The English trust is identified as the *waqf* in Islamic law, which developed during the 7th and 9th centuries.^[53] Other English legal institutions, such as the law schools known as Inns of Court in England, have some similarities with Islamic law.^[54] The discussion below will analyse whether the common law of England borrowed Islamic principles from Arab Sicily based on these principles:

A. Trust (*Waqf*)

Waqf is a charitable trust that aims to allocate property or income towards a religious or public purpose.^[55] There are two types of *waqf*: *waqf khairi* (which allocates both current and remainder income) and *waqf ahli* or *waqf dhurri* (which designates the remainder to a charitable purpose after a non-charitable income interest ends).^[56] Islamic law governs the *waqf* and comprises an equal footing of ordinances regarding worship, rituals, and political and legal rules.^[57] The *waqf* must be irrevocable, perpetual, and inalienable.^[58] It cannot depend on any third party, nor can a conventional option clause be used.^[59] The Maliki school of law allows *waqf* with a limited time or series of lives.^[60] *Waqf* property is inalienable and cannot be sold, disposed of, mortgaged, gifted, inherited, attached, or alienated in any way.^[61] However, it can be exchanged for equivalent property or sold if the price is reinvested in another property.^[62] The *waqif* (the owner) must

be in full possession of his faculties, be of age, and be a free man.^[63] The property constituting the trust must be tangible, immobile, and must yield income.^[64] Islamic law does not mandate a specific way to create a *waqf*. The *waqif* can make the declaration orally or in writing^[65] and the terms can include the appointment of the trustee, the selection of beneficiaries, and the distribution of *waqf* income.^[66] The founder could appoint himself a trustee or retain the right to modify the terms of the *waqf*.^[67] The *waqf* must not violate any of the tenets of Islam, and it must have an ultimate charitable object.^[68] The motive for creating a charitable trust is to perform good works and please God. The law of *waqf* is the only form of perpetuity in Islam and can be used for various purposes.^[69]

During the governance of Roger II and King Frederick II (r. 1198–1250) in Sicily,^[70] there was a notable rise in Islamic influence, further facilitating the transfer of practices and concepts related to *waqf* to Europe.^[71] Walter de Merton, the founder of Merton College, Oxford, played a crucial role in incorporating principles such as *waqf* into the establishment of Merton College.^[72] As a prominent clergyman and government official in England, Merton had significant dealings with Sicily during his tenure as Chancellor of England.^[73] His involvement in diplomatic affairs, particularly those concerning Sicily, exposed him to Middle Eastern influences, including the institution of *waqf*.^[74] Moreover, Merton's interactions with Crusaders and other visitors to the Middle East, as well as his access to the New Temple in England, which served as the headquarters of the Knights Templar with ties to the Middle East, likely contributed to his understanding of *waqf* principles.^[75]

The establishment of Merton College went through several stages, initially resembling charitable trusts like *waqf*, before being formally recognised in 1274.^[76] The 1264 statutes governing Merton College can be analysed within the *waqf* tradition, demonstrating potential similarities between the establishment of Merton College and Islamic charitable trusts.^[77] Thus, the borrowing of *waqf* principles from Arab Sicily to England, represented through the establishment of Merton College, underscores broader cultural exchanges and influences between the two regions during the medieval period.^[78]

It is worth noting that the 1264 statutes of Merton College align with *waqf* requirements without contravening Islamic principles. Although some aspects of Walter de Merton's trust may differ slightly, they do not contradict the basic principles of *waqf*, considering the founder's freedom in setting the terms of the trust within Islamic law. There is speculation that Merton might have been inspired by Islamic *waqf*, particularly in promoting education and safeguarding assets.^[79]

Nevertheless, according to Monica Gaudiosi's study, while there are similarities between *waqf* and the English trust system, it is uncertain if Merton intentionally imitated *waqf*, given the context of Merton College's establishment during the Crusades. This discussion prompts considerations regarding Islamic influence on Western law, particularly English law, which is often overlooked in Western legal studies. Acknowledging the similarities and differences between Islamic and English legal systems can enhance understanding of their histories, emphasising the importance of comparative legal research.

In conclusion, the examination of the potential borrowing of *waqf* principles from Arab Sicily to England, particularly in the establishment of Merton College, illuminates significant cultural exchanges and influences during the medieval period. The historical context, coupled with Walter de Merton's role and the alignment of Merton College's statutes with *waqf* traditions, suggests a plausible connection between the Islamic and English legal systems. While uncertainties remain regarding Merton's deliberate imitation of *waqf*, considering the context of the Crusades and the broader cultural milieu of the time, the discussion underscores the importance of comparative legal research in understanding the complex interplay between different legal traditions. Furthermore, it prompts a reconsideration of Western legal studies to acknowledge and explore the often-overlooked Islamic influences on Western law, particularly English law, enriching our understanding of legal histories and fostering appreciation for the interconnectedness of diverse legal traditions.

B. Supremacy of Law

The concept of a State being subordinate to the law is not unique to any particular legal system.^[80] Both Islamic law and common law recognise the existence of a higher law that supersedes the authority of the State.^[81] To better understand how the law above the State in common law is derived from the Islamic principles of Arab Sicily, it is important to delve deeper into the meaning of the State in both legal systems.

The State is usually defined as the collective agreement among individuals regarding the mechanisms for resolving disputes through the establishment of laws.^[82] It encompasses the political organisation of society, including the institutional framework within a defined geographical territory.^[83] This framework includes the government responsible for maintaining order and security, governance methods, legal framework, territorial boundaries, jurisdictional areas, and, ultimately, sovereignty.^[84]

In Islamic law, the concept of the State is absent in the Qur'an, but contemporary scholars agree that an Islamic State is both a political and moral entity.^[85] It emerges when a population is governed by an authority exercising sovereignty internally and maintaining independence externally from other governments.^[86] According to Professor Nehaluddin Ahmad, Islam recognises no laws other than Shariah law.^[87] Instead, the Islamic State itself is a historical construct, and legal principles were revealed by God through the Qur'an and Hadith, serving as foundational sources from which legal reasoning could be derived, as articulated in *fatwa* (legal opinions).^[88]

Islam emphasises that all officials in an Islamic State, whether the head of State or ordinary employees, are equal in the eyes of the law.^[89] No one is above the law or has immunity. Even ordinary citizens have the right to make claims or file legal complaints against the highest executive in the country.^[90]

This can be seen in the example of Caliph Umar, who said that he had seen the Prophet (peace be upon him) penalising himself for some shortcoming or failure. During the Battle of Badr, when the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him)

was straightening the rows of the Muslim army, he accidentally hit the belly of a soldier while trying to push him back in line. The soldier complained that he was hurt. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) immediately apologized and bared his belly, offering the soldier the option to take revenge by doing the same to him. The soldier, however, forgave the Prophet and kissed his abdomen instead, showing that forgiveness and compassion are important values in Islam.^[91]

In common law, the evolution of case law through judicial precedent required judges to reference a legal framework beyond the confines of the legal system itself.^[92] This framework often reflected moral consciousness reacting to societal context, resulting in the law holding a position above the State.^[93] Similarly, legal development was not solely reliant on State legislation and administrative regulations in Islamic law.^[94] Instead, it occurred through reasoning drawn from sources offering overarching principles of conduct. Judges based their decisions on traditional Islamic law sources and other factors such as *urf*' (custom), *darura* (necessity), and prevailing opinions among *fuqaha* (scholars) through *rajih* (preferred) and *mashur* (dominant).^[95] This approach in Islamic law led to the evolution of case law within the Maliki school of thought, resembling the development of common law in England.^[96] Islamic judges relied on traditional Islamic law sources and other factors to form judicial rulings, which were subsequently adhered to by later courts holding significant regulatory authority.^[97]

In conclusion, both common law and Islamic law have distinct qualities, but they both adhere to the idea that a higher law exists beyond the authority of the State. This highlights the significance of establishing legal systems on a moral and ethical foundation, irrespective of their legal customs. In simpler terms, they share similarities in the way they regulate general aspects of human life through the law.^[98]

C. Individualism

When delving into the topic of individualism and freedom, it cannot be denied that it is a legal concept that consistently presents a complex subject for both

jurists and philosophers.^[99] To delve deeper into this topic requires a lengthy explanation. However, we can clarify that individualism can be defined as a political and social philosophy that emphasises the moral values of individuals, individual interests, privacy, and mutual respect.^[100] It can also be explained as opposition to external control and power over individuals, especially by the State.^[101]

While the concepts of individualism and individual freedom are closely related, there are distinctions. Individual freedom refers to the innate condition of individuals to think, act, and pursue happiness without artificial constraints, and it is the ability to act without interference from others.^[102]

Professor Raymond Plant argued that the concept of individualism is indispensable for political science because concepts related to the social ‘whole’, such as ‘State’, ‘community’, ‘nation’, and ‘politic’, lack empirical sense unless they can be articulated in statements that refer solely to the empirically detectable behaviour of individuals.^[103] Additionally, it is important because there is unlikely to be an enlightened state until there is respect for individuality, and likewise, there will not be respect for individuality until there is an enlightened state.^[104]

Professor John Makdisi’s study highlights that in medieval Islam, the entire legal education system was designed to promote individualistic thinking. The doctoral degree, which grants the authority or licence to teach, was based on academic freedom to pursue independent research and express original opinions freely, without hindrance from the State.^[105]

The licence to teach emerged naturally in Islam because law fundamentally is an individualistic concept; conversely, when the licence to teach was introduced to the hierarchy of the Christian Church in the medieval period, it became contentious as it clashed with the Church’s power to sanction doctrine. Islam, in its reactive stance as a promoter of individualistic thought, not only allows but demands free play of opinions among legal theology doctors; the Catholic Church, in its activist role as the heir of Christ’s power, asserts that the opinions of legal theology doctors, the professorial magisterium, will not carry authority

unless and until they are accepted by the pastoral magisterium, consisting exclusively of Bishops in union with the Pope.^[106]

In conclusion, the concept of Islamic individualism, as exemplified by its emphasis on academic freedom, independent thought, and the pursuit of original opinions in legal education, demonstrates a parallel with the principles later embraced by common law systems. While historically distinct, the Islamic approach to fostering individualistic thinking within legal education provides an early precedent for the values that underpin modern conceptions of individual rights and academic freedom. Therefore, it can be argued that elements of Islamic individualism have indeed influenced and contributed to the development of common law principles, albeit through separate historical trajectories. This recognition of shared values and influences underscores the interconnectedness of legal traditions and highlights the rich diversity of sources that shape contemporary legal systems.

D. Freedom of Contract

The concept of freedom of contract in Islamic law is essential to understand within the framework of Islamic jurisprudence. Islamic jurists believe that the legal effects of a contract are determined by Allah, the Lawgiver Himself, making the terms of a contract dependent on the determinations set by Allah and not solely on the will of the contracting parties.^[107]

Professor Makdisi has described Islamic contract law as not being formalistic and flexible, allowing contracting parties full freedom to fulfil their needs and desires.^[108] While his statement is accurate, even though the existence of a contract stems directly from the will of the contracting parties, terms such as property transfer, leasing, and buying and selling are based on conditions set by the Lawgiver.^[109]

While Islamic contract law allows for flexibility and the freedom of contracting parties to fulfil their needs and desires, it is important to note that the general principles of Islamic contract law should not contradict Islamic principles and contracts involving elements such as usury or *riba* (excessive interest), *gharar*

(uncertainty), or *maysir* (gambling).^[110] If any of these elements are present, the contract is deemed invalid and void. This includes contracts involving sinful acts such as prostitution, alcohol, or pork as the subject of the contract, making them invalid and void.^[111]

Islamic contract law also provides an important space for the courts to intervene in a contract where the contract is unfair or there is an imbalance of obligations among the contracting parties.^[112]

Currently, all European countries, including England, recognise freedom of contract as a general principle of civil law.^[113] In this context, the role of the law in establishing or supporting freedom of contract is to ensure that legal institutions and aspects of commerce are arranged in such a way as to support free and open markets. Specifically, the role of contract law is primarily to support and facilitate market transactions, which can be referred to as the market-oriented vision of freedom of contract.^[114]

On the other hand, according to Professor John Cartwright, freedom of contract can also be seen as a moral principle, where the justification for contractual obligations lies in the choice or will of the individuals involved in the contract. This vision of freedom of contract, often expressed in continental Europe under the phrases ‘contractual autonomy’ or ‘autonomy of will’ and rooted in the philosophies of Rousseau and Kant, can be termed the ‘voluntary’ vision of freedom of contract.^[115]

According to Tedoradze Irakli’s study, the law has traditionally been silent on the procedure for forming contracts through negotiations.^[116] In the past, the sole requirement was an offer and acceptance; when the offer was accepted, agreement was reached; it was that simple.^[117] This approach is based on the aleatory theory of pre-contractual processes, which means that each party is responsible for the risks associated with negotiations; both parties’ benefits and losses are considered at risk in negotiations.^[118] This classic procedural theory is built on three assumptions: first, any interference would result in a violation of the principle of freedom of contract; second, any interference would make parties

think twice before initiating negotiations; and unless enforceable agreements bind parties, their behaviour should be disregarded as legally insignificant.^[119]

However, modern contract law recognises negotiation as a separate contract formation procedure.^[120] A balance must be struck between freedom of contract and protecting the rights and interests of the parties involved in negotiations.^[121] Since it is almost impossible to formulate detailed regulations, only general principles about pre-contractual conduct can be established.^[122]

In common law, there are situations mentioned in the case of *William Lacey Ltd v. Davis*,^[123] where it is viewed that when someone enters into negotiations, they consider it a risk. Where the associated costs are considered part of their ordinary business expenses, they expect to cover these costs from the successful contract proceeds. On the other hand, in the case of *Walford v. Miles*,^[124] the main question was whether parties could agree to negotiate in good faith. In this case, Lord Ackner stated that each party in the negotiation is entitled to pursue their own interests as long as they refrain from making false statements. They may also threaten to withdraw from negotiations to obtain better terms and conditions. However, imposing an obligation to negotiate in good faith is impractical and conflicts with the position of the negotiating parties.

Although common law takes a somewhat rigid approach in this regard, there are still ways to continue negotiations or seek compensation if negotiations are terminated. Even without a completed contract, the courts may recognise other agreements that confer specific rights during negotiations. Furthermore, the parties involved may be entitled to restitution if the other party benefits from a transaction without forming a contract (referred to as unjust enrichment).^[125]

Moreover, the parties involved may be liable for any losses suffered by the other party due to false representations, such as claims in tort, for example, when there was never an intention to form a contract or negligent misrepresentation. In England, only negative interests can be claimed, meaning specific performance compelling parties to reopen negotiations is not impossible.^[126]

In conclusion, in the context of freedom of contract, although there are some similarities between the principles of Islamic law and common law, it cannot be directly stated that common law directly adopts or borrows ideas from Islamic law. Both legal systems have different historical and philosophical roots, and significant differences exist in their approaches to freedom of contract.

Although both legal systems recognise freedom of contract, they do so on different grounds. In Islamic law, contracts are agreements subject to determinations set by Allah, and court intervention can occur to ensure fairness in contracts. Meanwhile, common law emphasises free and open markets and individuals' rights to pursue their interests, with court intervention tending to be more limited.

However, there are some similarities in the general principles underlying both legal systems, such as the emphasis on fairness in contracts and the protection of weaker parties. However, differences in historical roots, philosophy, and practical approaches between Islamic law and common law make definitive conclusions about direct borrowing or acceptance of ideas unclear.

So, while there are similarities in general concepts of freedom of contract between Islamic law and common law, there is no compelling evidence to suggest that common law directly “adopts” or “borrows” ideas from Islamic law in the context of freedom of contract.

E. Impartial Judge

Professor Jeffrey Shaman emphasises that judicial impartiality is a fundamental component of justice in the common law system.^[127] He asserts that judges are expected, above all, to act as impartial arbitrators, ensuring that legal disputes are resolved in accordance with the law, devoid of bias or prejudice.^[128] The principle of judicial impartiality is mandated by statutory and common law, as well as being required by the Code of Judicial Conduct, to ensure a fair legal process.^[129]

However, the question arises as to whether the concept of an impartial judge has been adopted and borrowed through the Islamic jurisprudence of Arab Sicily or

vice versa. This can be observed in the study conducted by Professor Makdisi, wherein the concept of an impartial judge already existed during the Norman rule. Similarly, within Islam, this concept is evident, as the duty of the *qadi* entails treating both parties fairly.^[130]

Ahmad ibn Yahya al-Wansharisi, a 16th-century Maliki scholar, once likened those who evade justice to wood thrown into fire.^[131] Therefore, the *qadi* plays a crucial role in resolving conflicts between two parties.^[132] Even in the presence of conflicting evidence, a resolution must be reached.^[133] If persistent disagreement persists in a case, it indicates that the involved parties are not yet sufficiently informed to make a decision. Consequently, the *qadi* may initiate further investigation or postpone the decision until they are more fully informed.^[134]

In conclusion, examining judicial impartiality reveals intriguing parallels between the common law tradition and Islamic jurisprudence. While Professor Jeffrey Shaman underscores the importance of impartiality within the common law system, it becomes apparent through the research of Professor Makdisi that similar principles existed in earlier historical contexts, such as during Norman rule. This suggests a potential exchange or convergence of ideas across legal traditions over time. Additionally, the shared emphasis on fairness and equitable treatment in both the common law and Islamic legal systems, as highlighted by figures like Ahmad ibn Yahya al-Wansharisi (b. 1430–1508), underscores the universal significance of impartiality in the pursuit of justice. Thus, while rooted in distinct cultural and historical contexts, the principle of judicial impartiality resonates across legal traditions, serving as a cornerstone for equitable legal processes worldwide.

F. *Res Judicata*

The full Latin maxim of this term is *res judicata pro veritate accipitur*, which essentially translates to ‘a matter adjudged is taken as truth’.^[135] *Res judicata* is a principle accepted by all courts in modern common law that states that legal disputes must come to an end.^[136] In other words, when a court makes a final

decision on a claim, it acts as a permanent barrier to further legal action involving the same claim.^[137]

This principle helps resolve conflicts by closing court cases and has been embraced by English law for jury verdicts.^[138] It is important to note that *res judicata* should not be confused with the doctrine of *stare decisis*, which is a modern common law principle stating that when a court applies a legal principle to the facts of a case, it will adhere to and apply it to all future cases with similar relevant facts. The doctrine of *stare decisis* was not accepted in England until the 19th century.^[139]

The origins of the doctrine of *res judicata* can be traced back to the 9th century, when Islamic courts adhered to a similar principle.^[140] However, there were exceptions, and decisions could be overturned if there were legal errors, but not for factual errors. Therefore, even if witnesses retract their statements, a decision cannot be overturned. If their statements are not retracted, witnesses who have lied can be punished and held responsible for the damage they caused. In the view of al-Qarafi (a 16th-century Maliki jurisprudence scholar), witnesses who give false testimony are considered not to be of good faith, and the court's decision remains unalterable.^[141]

However, a case study conducted in 1910 found a case from the 9th century where a decision was reconsidered and overturned by another judicial authority.^[142] The findings of this study changed the views of some scholars, noting that Islamic law does not recognise the concept of *res judicata* and the Islamic political body does not support the concept of *finis litium* (end of dispute).^[143] Reuben Levy suggested that in some cases, unfair heirs to a judge could affect overturning a decision, leading to a small paradigm shift among Islamicists as the important mechanism for reversing judicial decisions in Islamic law was overlooked.^[144]

To conclude, the origins of *res judicata* can be traced back to Islamic courts during the 9th century. However, whether the concept was directly borrowed from common law remains unclear. Professor Hanskin's findings shed light on the main factors that could answer the question of how England formed relations with Arab Sicily at that time. It may be possible that the principle was transmitted

through the influence of Islamic law on European legal systems during that period. Nevertheless, the concept of *res judicata* has been embraced by common law and is considered a fundamental principle in modern legal systems.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study aims to critically examine the historical connections between classical Islamic law, as applied in Arab Sicily, and certain legal principles found in the common law of England. The study focused on specific legal principles, their origins, and a comparison of similarities and differences between the two legal systems, particularly regarding concepts such as *waqf*, the supremacy of law over the State, individualism, freedom of contract, impartial judges, and the doctrine of *res judicata*.

It is important to note that Norman rule in Sicily during the 11th and early 12th centuries was not a time of cultural eradication but rather a time of integration and acceptance.^[145] The Normans embraced the unique features of Islamic culture and allowed the Muslim community to continue practising their customs freely.^[146] Factors that answer the question of how England formed relations with Arab Sicily at that time include the forms of government and courts in Northern and Southern Normandy, which exhibited potential mutual influence.^[147]

The relationship between King Henry II and King Roger II became closer when King William I and Princess Joan married on 13 February 1177, opening opportunities for both parties to continue monitoring conditions and drawing inspiration from each other's administrative systems. Thomas Brown, a Sicilian official sent to the Court of Henry II, demonstrated his ability as a valuable source of information on the administrative and economic system in Sicily.^[148]

The examination of the potential borrowing of *waqf* principles from Arab Sicily to England, particularly in the establishment of Merton College, illuminates significant cultural exchanges and influences during the medieval period.^[149] Both Islamic law and common law recognise the existence of a higher law that supersedes the authority of the State, highlighting the significance of establishing legal systems on a moral and ethical foundation.^[150]

Elements of Islamic individualism have indeed influenced and contributed to the development of common law principles, albeit through separate historical trajectories.^[151] While there are some similarities in general principles underlying both legal systems, there is no compelling evidence to suggest that common law directly “adopts” or “borrows” ideas from Islamic law in the context of freedom of contract.^[152]

The analysis of judicial impartiality reveals intriguing parallels between the common law tradition and Islamic jurisprudence. While Professor Jeffrey Shaman underscores the importance of impartiality within the common law system, it becomes apparent that similar principles existed in earlier historical contexts, such as during Norman rule.^[153] Last but not least, the origins of *res judicata* can be traced back to Islamic courts during the 9th century, but it remains unclear whether the concept was directly borrowed from common law.^[154]

In appreciation of the rich historical tapestry uncovered in this study, it is evident that the interplay between Islamic and common law traditions has contributed to the development of legal systems globally. This examination not only deepens our understanding of legal history but also underscores the importance of cultural exchange and mutual respect in shaping legal frameworks. It is recommended that future research continue to explore these connections, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the complex evolution of legal principles and their cross-cultural influences.

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